

Mixed Ligand Anionic Complexes of Nickel(II)

BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA, A. PANDA and S. K. PUJHARI

Department of Chemistry, Fanchayat College, Bargarh, Sambalpur
and

S. GURU

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack (Orissa)

M. nuscript received 16 November 1979, accepted 20 December 1979

Tetrathiocyanato Nickel(II) complex was reacted with a number of nitrogen donor ligands and a sulfur donor ligand and complexes of the composition $[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_4\text{L}_2]$ where L is pyridine, γ -picoline, quinoline, iso-quinoline, 2,6 lutidine, diethylamine, quinaldine, piperidine, $[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_4\text{L}]$ where L is ethylenediamine, *o*-phenylenediamine and $[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_3\text{L}]$ where L is oxine and piperidylthiocarbamate were isolated. These have been characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR and electronic spectral studies.

A number of simple and mixed ligand anionic complexes of Nickel(II) have been reported¹ of the composition $[\text{QH}]_2[\text{NiX}_4]$ where QH is a quaternary halide and tetrahedral configuration has been suggested for them. Also complexes of the composition $[\text{MLX}_3]^-$ where M is a bivalent metal like Co(II), Ni(II) or Zn(II) and X is Cl^- , Br^- , I^- and L is a nitrogen, phosphorous or arsenic ligand have been prepared^{2,3} earlier and established as tetrahedral compounds. Even though $[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_4]^{--}$ has been long since known as a tetrahedral species, little work has been done to change the stereochemistry of these complexes by reacting with other nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur ligands. To increase the coordination number, particularly to synthesise compounds of co-ordination number five, we have been trying⁴ to synthesise anionic mixed ligand complexes starting from these types of tetrahedral compounds. In this communication we report a number of hexacoordinated and two penta-coordinated mixed ligand anionic (thiocyanate) complexes using different ligand donor atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. An ethanolic solution of nickel thiocyanate was treated with an ethanolic solution of tetramethylammonium thiocyanate in 1 : 2 proportion when green crystalline compound of ditetramethylammonium tetrathiocyanato-nickel(II) was separated out. This was then filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuo.

The mixed ligand complexes were prepared by adding requisite amount (1 : 2 ratio) of ligands separately to ethanolic suspension of ditetramethylammonium tetrathiocyanato-nickel(II) and refluxing

for about 30 minutes. On cooling, crystalline compounds separated out which were then filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuo.

Discussion

On the basis of analysis and conductance data, the complexes have the composition $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_4\text{L}_2]$ where L is pyridine, γ -picoline, quinoline, isoquinoline, quinaldine, piperidine, 2,6 lutidine, diethylamine, $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_4\text{L}]$ where L is ethylenediamine, *o*-phenylenediamine and $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_3\text{L}]$ where L is oxine and piperidylthiocarbamate. All the complexes are light blue, green or violet crystalline compounds, soluble in acetone, in which medium the Δ_M values are around 250 mhos cm^2 indicating 2 : 1 electrolytic nature of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate the presence of two unpaired electrons and the μ_{eff} values are characteristic of spin-free octahedral complexes except with oxine and piperidylthiocarbamate. The magnetic moment values of these complexes are quite low (Table 1).

In the infrared spectra, absorption bands are noticed at 760 (s), 950 (vs) and 1490 (vs) cm^{-1} , characteristic of the tetramethylammonium ion, modified due to complexation. Very sharp absorption bands are absorbed $\sim 2060 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ of thiocyanate. In addition, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ bands have been observed at 1235 and 1200 cm^{-1} for the thiocarbamate and oxine complexes respectively. In case of oxine complex, $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ has disappeared indicating co-ordination of the oxine molecule through the hydroxyl oxygen. Most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen, oxygen

TABLE 1—COLOUR, ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	Colour	%Nickel		%SCN		%Nitrogen		ΔM mhos cm^2	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(C\equiv N)$	$\nu(M-N)$
		Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.				
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4]$	Blue	12.97	13.10	54.62	52.87	16.74	16.86	240	2.9	2055	385, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4PY_2]$	Bluish violet	9.68	9.83	38.54	38.87	18.65	18.76	238	3.1	2060	375, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4(\gamma\text{-pi})_2]$	Violet	9.24	9.38	36.89	37.13	17.62	17.92	2.20	3.1	20.70	380, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4Q_2]$	Bluish violet	8.29	8.42	33.07	33.29	15.91	16.06	230	2.9	20.60	370, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4IQ_2]$	Light violet	8.37	8.42	33.14	33.29	15.87	16.06	245	3.0	20.70	390, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4Qn_2]$	Blue	7.92	8.10	31.94	32.16	15.18	15.45	236	3.2	2070	380, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4(2,6\text{ lut})_2]$	Green	8.87	8.99	35.27	35.54	17.24	17.45	240	3.1	2055	385, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4(pip)_2]$	Light yellow	9.53	9.64	37.86	38.11	18.16	18.39	225	2.9	2065	380, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4(DEA)_2]$	Green	9.96	10.04	39.32	39.69	19.08	19.32	230	3.0	2060	390, 360
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4Pdte]$	Olive green	10.58	10.58	32.04	32.17	15.27	15.53	1.98	2.0	2070	385, 260 (M-S)
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_3Oxine]$	Light green	10.94	11.16	32.88	33.11	15.58	15.97	235	2.2	2070	390, 450 (M-O)
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4en]$	Green	15.28	15.34	29.97	30.30	28.94	29.23	240	2.9	2060	370, 350
$[L]_2[Ni(SCN)_4o\text{-PhDA}]$	Violet	13.51	13.64	26.63	26.9	26.05	26.26	245	3.1	2070	380, 350

$L = Me_4N^+$ cation, Py=Pyridine, $\gamma\text{-pic} = \gamma\text{-picoline}$, Q=Quinoline, IQ=I-quinoline, Qn=quinaldine, 2,6-lut = 2,6-lutidine, Pip=piperidine, DEA=Diethylamine, Pdte=Piperidyl dithiocarbamate, en=ethylenediamine, o-PhDA=o-Phenylenediamine.

and sulfur ligands have been modified due to bonding with the metal ion. Evidence for the co-ordination of the bases have been further substantiated by appearance of bands $\sim 350\text{-}390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the low frequency region assignable⁵ to $\nu(M-N)$. In addition, for the oxine and dithiocarbamate complex $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-S)$ appear ~ 460 and $\sim 260\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

In the electronic spectra of the complexes with nitrogen ligands, three absorption bands are observed around 9-9.5, 11-13, 24-26 k.k. region attributable to the three characteristic transitions of Nickel(II) ion in an octahedral^{6,4} environment. The low molar absorptivity values are also in conformity with this formulation. Complexes with oxine and piperidyl dithiocarbamate have two absorption bands ~ 25.5 and ~ 20.2 k.k. region, attributable to $3B_1 \rightarrow 3E'$ and $3B_1 \rightarrow 3E''$ transitions. This is in conformity with earlier reports on penta-coordinated complexes of Nickel(II)⁷⁻⁹. The magnetic moment values are also low which supports the configuration predicted by electronic spectra. Hence these two complexes are presumably penta-coordinated. However, X-ray crystallography

study will reveal the exact stereochemistry of the complexes.

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